

Proton Magnetic Resonance and Electron Spin Resonance of Synthetic Humic Acids

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The proton magnetic resonance (pmr) technique has become a promising tool for obtaining structural information on humic substances¹. Oka *et al.*² and Lakatos and Miesel³ assigned the region δ 4.0–5.5 to lactone protons but Ruggiero *et al.*⁴ assigned this to exchangeable protons. The paramagnetism of humic compounds may arise from variety of sources⁵. Atherton *et al.*⁶ and Sensi and Schnitzer⁷ believed that the humic acid is a mixture of free radicals of the semiquinone ion type. The peculiar stability of the free radical is demonstrated by retention of the electron spin resonance (esr) signal after boiling humic acid with 6 N HCl or with 4 N NaOH, probably due to its association with an extended conjugated system. The complete spectra in solid state showed two main resonance⁵ at $G \sim 4.125$ and ~ 2.00 . Similar esr signal at ~ 2.00 for humic compounds was reported by Schnitzer and Skinner⁸ and concluded that the nature of free radical involved at $G \sim 2.00$ would be a matter of conjecture, but likely possibilities are semiquinone radicals associated with a condensed ring system or a mixture of two or more different types of radicals. It was predicted⁵ that the signal at $G \sim 4.125$ is due to Fe^{3+} chelate. A novel approach was developed by Schnitzer and Levesque⁹ for assessing the degree of humification of peats at various stages of decomposition. The free radicals that are involved in humification are substituted semiquinones, whose concentration increases with increase in humification.

The object of this study is to get an idea, from such assignment of G -values, about the nature of humification of synthetic products corresponding to different periods of condensation, and to relate their pmr signals in relation to aromatic and aliphatic (amino acid) source.

Results and Discussion

The assignment of nitrogen-containing and nitrogen-free synthetic products, obtained from alkaline oxidative condensation of vanillic acid with an amino acid, and self-condensation of vanillic acid respectively¹⁰, are presented in Table 1.

Starting material	Synthetic product	Period of condensation (h)
Vanillic acid and L(-)-aspartic acid (acidic)	HA ₁	2, 5
Vanillic acid and glycine (neutral)	HA ₂	2, 5
Vanillic acid and L(+)-lysine (basic)	HA ₃	2, 5
Vanillic acid (self-condensation)	HA ₄	5

The pmr spectra of amino acids have broad bands at δ 1.57–1.94, 2.88–3.14 and 3.58–4.06, the last one being due to CH_2 protons attached to zwitterion carboxyl and amino groups. For vanillic acid the spectral bands are observed at δ 3.4–3.76 for methoxyl group, δ 6.84–6.92 and 7.44–7.52 for aromatic protons *m* to carboxyl and *o* to carboxyl respectively, and δ 9.84–9.94 for phenolic groups. The values obtained in the present investigation corroborate with the values for glycine and lysine¹¹. For vanillic acid, the theoretical¹² δ values for ring protons are calculated from the shifts in the position of benzene protons caused by different substituents (Table 2).

The pmr spectra of the four synthetic humic acids HA₁, HA₂, HA₃ and HA₄ were very similar (Table 3). The aliphatic region of amino acids was obliterated in the spectra of the nitrogen-containing humic acids due to strong signal of DMSO at δ

TABLE 2

Proton	(a)	(b)	(c)
Benzene	7.27	7.27	7.27
OH	-0.4	-0.4	-0.4
COOH	0.8	0.15	0.8
OMe	-0.2	-0.2	-0.2
	7.47	6.82	7.47

3.3–3.4 ppm. The spectra have broad signals at δ 1.24–2.52, 3.80–3.86 and 6.17–7.66. Methoxyl signal (δ 3.60–3.86) present in HA₁ and HA₂, is very weak in HA₃ and HA₄, and practically indistinguishable with the very strong band for DMSO solvent at δ 3.3–3.4. The weak signals for aliphatic and aromatic protons are found at δ 1.20–2.52 and 6.30–7.60 respectively. It is observed that the methoxyl group in vanillic acid is also present after condensation, but with lowering in intensity, indicating its lower content in the synthetic products. The similar signals for both nitrogen-containing and nitrogen-free synthetic products at δ 6.50–7.60 indicate the presence of similar types of unaffected aromatic protons. The strong signals for aromatic protons in vanillic acid coalesce in synthetic products indicating complexity in the aromatic region. It is pertinent to note that Ludemann *et al.*¹³ and Lentz *et al.*¹⁴ observed signals for a number of soil humic acids at δ 1.0–2.5, 3.8 and 6.5–8.5, which are characteristics of the aliphatic, methoxy and aromatic regions respectively.

TABLE-3 MAJOR NMR SIGNALS (δ) OF SYNTHETIC HUMIC ACIDS

Vanillic acid	HA ₁	HA ₂	HA ₃	HA ₄	Assignment
-	1.2	-1.24	1.2	1.2	Aliphatic protons
3.4	3.37	3.44	3.4	3.4	Contaminated DMSO protons
3.76	3.6–3.8	-	-	-	Methoxy proton
6.84, 6.92	6.5	6.36–7.00	7.52–7.66	7.44–7.60	Protons <i>ortho</i> and <i>meta</i>
7.44, 7.52	7.36–7.6	7.42–7.58	(Broad band at δ 6.8 centered at above region)		COOH in aromatic ring

constant with progressive humification and with formation of Fe-chelate, but for $G \sim 4.125$, there is slight increase of values. The appearance of signal at $G \sim 4.125$ in both Fe-free and Fe-complex indicates that the same signal is not due to Fe-chelate formation of the compound. It is further supported by the fact that the magnetic moment for high-spin Fe-chelate with the orbital motion making its full contribution to spin magnetic (which is nil in fact), is 5.92 EM which corresponds to $G \sim 2.00$. It appears from the present study that during humification or Fe-chelate formation of humic acid, the nature of free radical remains the same and confined to semi-quinone radical⁶, the formation of which is the primary step in oxidative condensation process for both nitrogen-containing and nitrogen-free synthetic products. However, the appearance of signal at $G \sim 4.125$ remains unresolved.

TABLE 4—SUMMARY OF RESULTS FOR ESR SPECTRAL MEASUREMENT FOR SYNTHETIC HUMIC ACIDS AND THEIR Fe-CHELATE

Sample	Condensation period (h)	G value			
		Humic Acid		Fe-chelate	
HA ₁	2	1.990	4.182	-	-
	5	1.990	4.130	-	-
HA ₂	2	1.994	4.183	-	-
	5	1.990	4.130	2.147	4.224
HA ₃	2	2.000	4.291	-	-
	5	1.990	4.209	2.027	4.250
HA ₄	5	1.978	4.067	-	-

Experimental

The pmr spectra were recorded on a FX 100 JEOL, Japan spectrometer. The measurement for humic acids and vanillic acid was done in DMSO solvent while D₂O was used for amino acids. The esr spectra were recorded on a Varian 109C E-line X-band spectrometer. The G values were calculated from the relation, $G_{\text{sample}} = (H_{\text{DPPH}} / H_{\text{sample}}) G_{\text{DPPH}}$, where H is the magnetic field strength (scan range 8000 Gauss) and G_{DPPH} is used as the standard for free electron spin, the value being taken as 2.002322.

The Fe-complexes of humic acid composition were made by shaking the materials with FeCl₃ and finally dialysing the products. Humic acid compositions prepared by 2 and 5 h of condensation were used for the measurements.

Table 4 shows that G value ~ 2.00 remains

NOTE

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